

Knowledge Workers in the Global Innovation Index

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In the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII), knowledge workers are highly skilled professionals whose main contribution to the economy is based on their ability to generate, manage, and apply knowledge. These professionals play a crucial role in the innovation process, as they use intellectual skills, creativity, and advanced knowledge to solve complex problems and create added value in their respective fields. Knowledge workers include engineers, scientists, researchers, analysts, software developers, highly specialized technicians, and other professionals involved in sectors such as research and development (R&D), information and communication technology (ICT), and education. The GII measures the impact of these workers by analyzing factors such as the density of researchers, the development of advanced human capital, and the diffusion of technical and scientific knowledge. The contribution of knowledge workers is fundamental to a country's economic competitiveness, as they foster technological innovation and adaptation to new markets and global challenges. Their presence and activity largely determine a country's ability to transform innovation into sustainable economic growth and social progress. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Knowledge Workers in 2022. The data on knowledge workers in 2022, as measured in the Global Innovation Index (GII), provide a detailed overview of the distribution of highly skilled labor across various countries. Knowledge workers, including professionals such as engineers, researchers, scientists, and IT specialists, are essential for technological development and innovation, as their contribution is directly linked to a country's ability to translate advanced knowledge into economic growth. At the top of the ranking, China (77.8) is followed by well-known innovation leaders such as Sweden (77.1), South Korea (75.2), and the United States (75). These countries demonstrate a strong presence of knowledge workers, which is the basis of their global leadership in innovation. China, in particular, has invested heavily in higher education and the creation of a technology-friendly ecosystem, solidifying its position as one of the emerging economies in the field of science and technology. South Korea has also benefited from government policies focused on human capital development in technology and research sectors. The United States remains in a prominent position due to its historical leadership in scientific and technological research, despite increasing competition from countries like China and South Korea. The presence of world-class universities and a robust system of innovation incentives contribute to its high share of knowledge workers. At the same time, Belgium (74.4), Singapore (69.6), and Luxembourg (68.9) stand out as smaller nations that, despite their limited size, have developed a high level of professional expertise through targeted policies to attract global talent and investments in high-tech sectors. Among European countries, France (68.4) and Switzerland (67.9) confirm their position as hubs for knowledge workers, thanks to their advanced economies and educational systems that support the development of highly qualified professionals. Israel (67.9) stands out for its ability to attract talent in the technology sector and its vibrant startup ecosystem, supported by a strong culture of innovation and investments in research and development. In the mid-range of the ranking, countries like Germany (60.7), the United

Kingdom (62.6), and Australia (62.4) maintain a robust share of knowledge workers but show signs of growing competition from emerging economies. Germany, traditionally considered a manufacturing and technological powerhouse, may face challenges in keeping pace with rapidly developing countries like China and South Korea. Within Europe, Italy (39.5) ranks lower than other continental countries. This figure reflects the need to improve the educational system and promote policies that encourage the attraction and development of knowledge workers. Although Italy has an excellent academic tradition, there is a gap in its ability to retain and develop highly skilled professionals, which limits the impact of innovation. At the bottom of the ranking are countries such as Bangladesh (11.8), Yemen (10.3), and various African nations like Ethiopia (5.3) and Mozambique (5.1). These countries face significant challenges in education and the development of technological skills, which hinders their innovative potential. The lack of investment in educational and technological infrastructure is one of the main factors contributing to these low scores. A particular case is Saudi Arabia, which presents a score of zero. This could be the result of difficulties in accurately measuring the highly skilled workforce in the country or could reflect a lack of development in this type of skill. Despite recent efforts to diversify the Saudi economy and invest in technology, the historical dependence on the oil industry has likely delayed the growth of knowledge-based sectors. In conclusion, the data on knowledge workers highlight a strong disparity between advanced countries and emerging economies. While nations like China, Sweden, and the United States continue to lead thanks to massive investments in human capital, many developing countries struggle to build the necessary infrastructure to support the growth of a highly skilled workforce. The ability to attract, train, and retain knowledge workers will be crucial for the future economic and technological development of many of these nations.

Knowledge Workers Between 2013 and 2022. The data on the number of knowledge workers for the period 2013-2022 show a complex and varied global picture. Knowledge workers include highly skilled professionals in fields such as technology, science, education, and innovation, and their number is often considered a key indicator of a country's economic development and innovation. The analysis of changes between 2013 and 2022 highlights positive trends for some countries, while others have seen significant declines. Some countries have seen a significant increase in the number of knowledge workers. These include Albania (+41.6%), Belgium (+14.1%), Cyprus (+34.7%), China (+23.7%), and Sweden (+16.1%). These countries have invested in targeted policies to strengthen human capital and their capacity for innovation, increasing training and employment in knowledge-intensive sectors. For example, Albania experienced a 41.6% growth in the number of knowledge workers, likely due to policies incentivizing technological and scientific training along with greater integration into international markets. China continued to invest heavily in higher education, research, and technological development, consolidating its position as one of the world's leading innovation hubs. In Europe, Belgium and Sweden also saw significant increases thanks to policies promoting employment in technological and scientific sectors. However, many countries have experienced a significant reduction in the number of knowledge workers. Some of the most drastic declines occurred in countries such as Angola (-50.26%), Benin (-75.69%), Bosnia and Herzegovina (-51.92%), Brazil (-4.57%), and Italy (-37.30%). This reduction may reflect structural problems related to economic instability, lack of investment in education and advanced training, or brain drain to countries with better opportunities. For example, Italy experienced a reduction of more than 37% in knowledge workers, a worrying figure that reflects the country's difficulty in retaining talent and attracting investments in innovative sectors. Even Brazil, despite being one of the largest economies in Latin America, saw a contraction in the number of knowledge workers, likely due to the political and economic crises that characterized the country during this period. Countries such as Burkina Faso (-61.3%), Bangladesh (-57.55%), and Mozambique (-56.78%) experienced huge declines in the number

of knowledge workers. These developing countries often suffer from a lack of investment in strategic sectors such as higher education and technology. Additionally, brain drain and emigration to countries with better economic opportunities likely contributed to this decline. Some countries have shown particular trends. For example, Belarus experienced a relatively moderate decline (-6.32%) despite economic and political difficulties, suggesting some resilience in maintaining a qualified workforce. The United States (+3.16%), one of the leading countries in terms of knowledge workers, saw modest growth, confirming its consolidated position as a global leader in innovation. The global picture of knowledge workers highlights a growing polarization between countries that continue to invest in education and innovation and those facing severe economic and social challenges. Countries that have managed to maintain or increase the number of knowledge workers are likely to benefit from greater economic growth and competitiveness, while those that have experienced drastic declines will face tougher challenges in closing the technological and innovation gap.

Conclusions. The number of knowledge workers decreased between 2013 and 2022 on average from 44.59 to 35.44 units, equivalent to a decrease of -20.53%. The top performers, i.e., the countries where the value of knowledge workers grew significantly between 2013 and 2022, are: Albania (+41.58%), Cyprus (+34.71%), Nigeria (+32.97%), China (+23.69%), and South Korea (+18.24%). The worst performers, i.e., the countries where the value of knowledge workers decreased, are: Egypt (-68.28%), Madagascar (-69.90%), Mali (-75.00%), Benin (-75.69%), and Ethiopia (-78.46%).

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Performance	Country	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Best Performance	Albania	29,1	41,2	12,1	41,58
	Cyprus	36,3	48,9	12,6	34,71
	Nigeria	27,9	37,1	9,2	32,97
	China	62,9	77,8	14,9	23,69
	Korea, Rep.	63,6	75,2	11,6	18,24
Worse Performance	Egypt, Arab Rep.	43,5	13,8	-29,7	-68,28
	Madagascar	19,6	5,9	-13,7	-69,90
	Mali	20,4	5,1	-15,3	-75,00
	Benin	39,9	9,7	-30,2	-75,69
	Ethiopia	24,6	5,3	-19,3	-78,46

2022

Fonte: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/web/global-innovation-index>

